

Key Strategies for a Competitive Supply Chain

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Abstract : In this era of competitiveness, there is a growing need for supply chains also to become competitive enough to handle pressures like varying customer's expectations, low cost high quality products to be delivered at the minimum time and the most important is throat cutting competition at world wide scale. In the recent years, supply chain competitiveness has been, therefore, accepted as one of the most important philosophies in the supply chain literature and researchers have tried to identify variables of supply chain competitiveness. This paper highlights some of the concepts of supply chain competitiveness and tries to identify select variables on the basis of literature review. Further, the paper tries to highlight the importance of the identified variables in the achievement of supply chain competitiveness. The aim is to explore the the concept and to motivate researchers to further investigate the enexplored areas of this important subject domain.

Keywords : Supply Chain Competitiveness, Demand Management, Integration, Inventory Management, Flexibility, Information Technology.

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